

**PLACE AND ROLE OF GAMING TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING
ENGLISH IN PRIMARY SCHOOL**

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Annotation: The methodology of teaching a foreign language has its own approach to the definition of the concept of "games".

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The lesson was and remains the main element of the educational process, but its function and form of organization are significantly changing in the learning system. English is one of the most important subjects of the school curriculum, which every modern person should know. I consider the use of gaming technologies in English lessons an integral part of my work. After all, it is the game elements that are competently included in the educational process that can help in realizing the main goal of teaching a foreign language in the aggregate of its components in the formation of the communicative competence of students. While learning the alphabet, you can play a variety of spelling games for knowledge of the alphabet, for example: find a pair of ABC Games. The teacher should have two sets of cards with letters of the alphabet: uppercase and lowercase. At the beginning, the teacher talks about that the cards were lying on the table, suddenly a strong wind blew and all the letters were lost and asks for help to collect. Each student receives cards with letters. At the command of the teacher, everyone must find a mate. For strong students, you can offer a task at the end to line up in alphabetical order.

Another "multifunctional" game. All participants in the game stand in a circle. The student who starts the game calls any letter of the alphabet. The next one to receive the ball calls the next letters to the end of the alphabet. If he coped with the task, he is given the right to continue the game; The game "Snowball" or "snowballs"

is well known to all teachers. The rules of the game are simple: Students are offered a certain topic, for example, "Clothes", the first player says the word Dress, the next one says the first word, and then his own: dress, T-shirt, etc. The development of lexical skills occurs through riddles. Students are given homework to describe an animal, a house, a fairy-tale hero, without naming him. Checking homework takes place in the form of a "riddle contest". Such techniques allow not only to consolidate the studied vocabulary on a particular topic, but also to work out the grammatical structures of an affirmative sentence, a general question, a short and complete answer to it. So when working on the vocabulary "Products", "Clothes" in grades 3-4, a "shop", "school canteen" appears. Children are happy to get used to the role of a buyer or seller. On the counter of the store are various items of clothing or food that you can buy. Students go to the store, buy what they need: P1: Good morning! P2: Good morning! P1: Give me carrots and some milk, please P2: Here you are P1: Thank you P2: You are welcome. On the counter of the store are various items of clothing or food that you can buy. Students go to the store, buy what they need: P1: Good morning! P2: Good morning! P1: Give me carrots and some milk, please P2: Here you are P1: Thank you P2: You are welcome. On the counter of the store are various items of clothing or food that you can buy. Students go to the store, buy what they need: P1: Good morning! P2: Good morning! P1: Give me carrots and some milk, please P2: Here you are P1: Thank you P2: You are welcome.

Very exciting and mysterious game "Mystery box". For this game you will need one small box. We put objects inside and let the children take turns pulling out and naming what they got. You can put one item at a time, or you can put all at once. You can put only items on the topic that you are studying in the box, or you can mix them up on all the topics covered - this will be more interesting, because it will be more difficult for children to guess what is inside in advance. Before giving to a child, the box can be effectively shaken to create even more intrigue: Whose turn is it? It's my turn! Mystery box, mystery box, what's inside the mystery box? It's a/an...

Of particular interest are games in which, after listening to the text, it is necessary to play a scene according to the content of the text. In these games,

children demonstrate not only their listening skills, but also their artistic abilities. Who knows the numbers better: The class is divided into 2 or 3 teams. From each team, one person goes to the board, on which the numbers are written. The host calls any number, the student looks for it on the board and circles it with chalk. The one who circles the most numbers wins. Riddles about animals. The teacher reads riddles to students, students must guess them. "Merry Artists" The student goes to the blackboard, closing his eyes, draws an animal. The host calls the main parts of the body: Draw a nose, please.

Draw hair, please. Draw a tail, please. Members of both teams stand in a circle. The leader is in the center of the circle. He names mixed fruits and vegetables. When children hear the name of fruits, they clap once; when they hear the name of vegetables, they clap twice. The one who makes a mistake is out of the game. The team with the most players left is the winner.

Seasons: the teacher invites one of the students to think of any season and describe it without naming it. For example: It is cold. It is white. I ski. I skate. I throw snowballs. Students try to guess: Is it spring? Is it winter?

The winner is the one who correctly named the time of year. Puzzle games: Teacher: Mr. Greenwood invited forest school students to write a riddle about a school friend. You know them too, but can you guess who they are talking about?

- I have a friend. Is not a small. can read, write and count, but not well. He can run and jump and play. He cannot swim.

- I have a friend. Not is a big and fat. He cannot read and write, but he can run, sing, dance and play. He can fly!

Game "Translator": The teacher offers to watch one of the fragments of cartoons with subtitles in English. The student repeats the phrase after the speaker and translates into Russian. Thus, listening, vocabulary, grammar are practiced. The students enjoy the game immensely. Language material is easily assimilated. Gaming technologies are often very simple in their organization and do not require special equipment.

This is not a complete list of games that I use in my English lessons in elementary school: it can be replenished indefinitely. One game can simultaneously carry grammatical, lexical, and phonetic material. The game may be planned, or it may be improvisation. It can wedge into any stage of the lesson or permeate the entire lesson. For the teacher, the main thing to remember is that the game is only an element of the lesson, and it should serve to achieve the didactic goals of the lesson. Therefore, it is necessary to know exactly what kind of skill, ability is trained in this game, what the child did not know how to do before the game, and what he learned during the game.

Summing up the above, we can note the “for” the use of gaming technologies: gaming technologies contribute to increasing interest, activation and development of thinking; bears a health-saving factor in development and learning; there is a transfer of experience of older generations to younger ones; promotes the use of knowledge in a new situation; is a natural form of child labor, preparation for the future life; promotes team building and responsibility. The “cons” when using gaming technologies are as follows: complexity in organization and problems with discipline; preparation requires more time than its implementation; being carried away by the game shell, you can lose the educational content; inability to use on any material; difficulty in assessing students.

List of used literature:

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2. Puchkova Yu. Ya. Games in English lessons - M.: AST, 2003